

Mobile Cell-Free Massive MIMO: A Practical O-RAN Based Approach

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ABSTRACT Cell-Free Massive MIMO is a promising solution for next-generation radio access networks. Especially the user-centric variant, where users are served by a subset of access points, a cluster, has garnered significant interest. However, managing these clusters in case of user mobility remains a significant issue. Additionally, the practical implementation of such a network remains an open problem. This work introduces a realistic temporal channel model for Cell-Free Massive MIMO. Subsequently, we propose a framework to facilitate handover procedures in a distributed topology considering limited channel knowledge for cluster formation. Next, we develop two clustering and handover strategies: 1) a fixed clustering strategy where the central processing unit computes the ideal cluster when a cluster handover threshold is exceeded and 2) an opportunistic strategy where access points make autonomous decisions based on the local channel. Finally, we establish a significant connection between our findings and O-RAN, an emerging network architecture that offers open interfaces and network-wide control capabilities. Simulation results show that even low-complexity handover mechanisms can significantly improve spectral efficiency under user mobility compared to cellular networks.

INDEX TERMS Cell-Free Massive MIMO, Distributed Processing, Next-Generation Radio Access Networks, Scalable Implementation, Dynamic Clustering

I. Introduction

Next-generation wireless networks will demand enormous data rates. Recently, Cell-Free Massive MIMO (CF mMIMO) has emerged as a promising network architecture [2] for providing these rates. This architecture considers a large number of Access Points (APs) which cooperate via coherent joint transmission and reception [3] to serve users. However, allocating APs to users and seamless and efficient handover in such a system is still an open problem. Additionally, it is still unclear how to deploy such a network in a practical network architecture. At the same time, the recent emergence of O-RAN's open interfaces enables dynamic resource allocation, cost-effective scalability and many possibilities for network-wide optimisation. Hence, the combination of CF mMIMO and O-RAN demonstrates significant synergy and potential to address the challenges for future communication networks [4]–[6].

A. Cell-Free Massive MIMO

Traditional cellular architectures struggle to meet the demands of next-generation wireless networks because they are constrained by fixed cell boundaries and limited diversity. CF mMIMO offers a strong alternative by enabling joint user service from many APs without these aforementioned cell boundaries, significantly enhancing spectral efficiency and macro-diversity while reducing interference. Recently, user-centric CF mMIMO [7], where users are served by a selected cluster of APs that provide the best channel, has become the most popular variant due to its more practical nature and increased scalability. This scalability of CF mMIMO networks was recently recognised as an essential requirement [8] and requires significant effort. Many seminal works discuss networks with many APs which compute the lower parts of the physical layer and only a single Central Processing Unit (CPU) responsible for the higher parts of

the physical layer processing of the entire network [9], [10]. However, the centralisation of all computations in such a CPU must be avoided as this imposes immense requirements on that unit's fronthaul capacity and computing power.

As such, local processing schemes in which APs send already partially preprocessed estimates to the CPU have gained traction. Furthermore, distributed CPUs for increased scalability are explored in [11]–[13]. For Uplink (UL) combining, these smaller CPUs then locally combine the signal of their respective APs based on statistical knowledge of the received signals. Such schemes have been proposed for UL combining and Downlink (DL) precoding, but no such schemes have been proposed for cluster management. The reader is referred to [14]–[17] for a comprehensive overview of recent advances in CF mMIMO.

Unfortunately, efficiently managing CF mMIMO in the presence of user mobility remains a significant concern [18]. While the problem was studied in [19]–[22], these works 1) lack a tractable channel model to study handover in sub-6GHz correlated Rayleigh fading and 2) rely on a single centralised CPU for cluster reformulation and processing of the higher parts of the physical layer.

Xiao *et al.* [19] focus on performance analysis, using stochastic geometry to calculate handover frequency and its impact on average throughput. Their work does not consider novel methods for mobility management. Zaher *et al.* [21] and D'Andrea *et al.* [20] consider a DL channel in the mmWave band, which differs significantly from our use-case. This work considers an UL channel in the sub-6 GHz band. We propose a tractable channel model for studying mobility management in this scenario.

The cooperation between APs in CF mMIMO enables partial change in user-centric clusters under user mobility. This partial change, called a soft handover, enables much more efficient mobility management. D'Andrea *et al.* [20] discuss soft handover but focus on beamforming design that is more robust to the users' mobility. Unfortunately, if users move fast, the CPU becomes highly loaded with handover procedures. Furthermore, the authors do not address how the control plane can be persistent during these handovers. Zaher *et al.* [21] and Li *et al.* [22] also discuss the concept of soft handover. In their work, each user has a so-called 'Master AP,' which maintains a persistent connection. However, the aforementioned works require significant communication between APs when users connect, which limits scalability. This work proposes a distributed approach for mobility management to overcome this limitation.

Furthermore, all mentioned works assume full knowledge of large-scale fading between each user and each AP. This is unrealistic for large-scale CF mMIMO networks, as measuring path loss between every user and AP becomes impossible for large network sizes. Hence, this work explores limited shared information between the user and the network, i.e., the user does not know the channel to each AP in the network, and the network does not know the channel to every user.

This approach improves scalability significantly and is not considered in any current research.

B. O-RAN

The O-RAN framework offers a promising solution for practically enabling scalable and flexible CF mMIMO networks due to the functional split between O-RAN Distributed Units (O-DUs) and Radio Units (O-RUs), as well as the introduction of additional functional blocks for AI and containerised service orchestration. These include the Near-Real Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC), the Non-RT RIC, and the Service Management and Orchestration framework [23]. The reader is referred to [24] for an extensive overview of the O-RAN architecture. By leveraging these interfaces, cooperation and seamless handover can be achieved between O-RUs and O-DUs in an O-RAN network. Since the processing of the physical layer is split between the O-DU and O-RU, the architecture is well aligned with works on CF mMIMO that discuss a similar split between the APs and the CPU [25].

Previous works [4], [5], [26] have shown that by letting O-DUs collaboratively decode the user's signal, their performance can be greatly improved. To achieve such collaborative decoding, a mapping of state-of-the-art CF mMIMO decoding algorithms to the O-RAN architecture was proposed [5]. This solution maps the CPU to the Near-RT RIC and a set of cooperating O-DUs, and the APs are mapped to the O-RUs. Furthermore, those works discuss how the relevant O-RAN interfaces, such as the E2 (between O-DU and Near-RT RIC) and the fronthaul (between O-DU and O-RU), enable such distributed processing. They argue in favour of an inter-O-DU interface which allows cooperative precoding and decoding amongst O-DUs by partially merging their physical layers for selected users. This idea is then highly compatible with the aforementioned works on CF mMIMO that discuss collaborative CPUs [11]–[13]. Similarly, Ranjbar *et al.* [4] discuss the joint computation of a precoder across O-RUs and O-DUs. Unfortunately, a high degree of cooperation requires significant computing power and signalling capacity between the O-DUs due to the large amounts of channel state information (CSI) needed to calculate the combiner.

Those works have shown many synergies between O-RAN and CF mMIMO for static users. This work explores how to further integrate these promising technologies by proposing two clustering and handover algorithms. We extend this mapping by also considering user mobility and how the allocation of O-DUs and O-RUs to a user should change, resulting in a full (hard) or partial (soft) handover.

C. State-of-the-Art in Mobility Modeling

Currently, existing channel models for studying CF mMIMO often focus on small-scale fading dynamics and are thus unfit for studying long-term AP clustering evolutions. Many works [27]–[31] use the Jakes autocorrelation model, where

the different channels are assumed to be from the same distribution, and small-scale fading is modelled as an autoregressive function. However, this assumption fails to represent large-scale fading dynamics accurately. D’Andrea *et al.* [20] consider a mmWave channel consisting of one Line-of-Sight (LoS) and several Non-Line-of-Sight (NLoS) components, updated at discrete sampling times. The user’s location determines the Angle-of-Arrival (AoA) and the path loss; thus, the LoS component can be computed directly. The NLoS components are computed as an autoregressive function via Jakes’ autocorrelation model. This approach does not accurately model long-term fading dynamics and rich scattering environments. In [19], handover probability in cellular MIMO is studied using distance-based metrics via higher-order Voronoi regions. As such, they do not model the channel itself but only the movement of the UEs.

The authors of [21] use a blockage map and ray tracing for an urban location; hence, the shadowing is consistent between UEs and along the path of the UE. Unfortunately, it is computationally very taxing and scenario-specific. Since the ray tracer must compute each channel path separately, the number of paths that reach the receiver is usually quite large in sub-6 GHz frequencies.

The aforementioned shortcomings of the current state-of-the-art motivate us to develop a novel model. We extend the classical correlated Rayleigh fading channel model by incorporating a temporal evolution of large-scale fading parameters. These temporal evolutions include a deterministic component due to the user’s location and a stochastic component due to random shadow fading. The shadow fading is modelled as an autoregressive function based on empirical measurements [32].

D. Contribution

This paper studies user mobility in CF mMIMO and proposes centralised and distributed methods for cluster formation and handover management. We introduce four contributions to the current state-of-the-art:

- We introduce a tractable temporal channel model for CF mMIMO at sub-6 GHz frequencies based on empirical measurements. Unlike models that only consider small-scale fading evolution, our work considers large-scale fading changes. This enables the study of long-term user-centric clustering performance.
- We introduce two clustering and handover strategies: an **opportunistic** strategy where O-DUs can locally decide to serve specific users, and a **fixed** strategy where handover is computed at the near-RT RIC, a centralised processor.
- We map our handover solutions to the O-RAN framework and offer practical implementation guidelines. Our work establishes a framework that includes our notions of primary O-RU, primary O-DU, and measuring and serving clusters.

TABLE 1. List of the most commonly used acronyms

Acronym	Full Name
AP	Access Point
CPU	Central Processing Unit
O-RU	O-RAN Radio Unit
O-DU	O-RAN Distributed Unit
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
NLoS	Non-Line of Sight
AoA	Angle of Arrival
DL	Downlink
UL	Uplink
LSFD	Large Scale Fading Decoding

- We quantify computational and signalling costs associated with each proposed algorithm for a detailed cost/performance analysis.

Outline: First, we define our clustering strategies in Section II. In Section III, we give an overview of our CF mMIMO system model and extend it to allow for temporal evolution. Subsequently, in Section IV, we explain our handover strategies. In Section VI, we provide numerical results for the proposed solutions.

Notation: A diagonal matrix with the elements x_i on the main diagonal is denoted by $\text{diag}(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_N)$. The cardinality of a set \mathcal{S} is written as $|\mathcal{S}|$. For matrices and vectors alike, \mathbf{A}^T is the transpose, \mathbf{A}^H is the Hermitian conjugate of the matrix, and \mathbf{A}^* is the complex conjugate. The l ’th element of vector \mathbf{a} is denoted by $[\mathbf{a}]_l$. The expected value of x is denoted by $\mathbb{E}\{x\}$. We list our commonly used acronyms in Table 1 and symbols in Table 2.

Reproducible Research: The simulation code for this paper is available at: <https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/u0149002/oran-handover>

II. Cluster Formation

Managing user-O-RU clusters in CF mMIMO networks is crucial for balancing high performance and scalable processing. In this section, we explain how the initial clusters are formed. Before the cluster that will serve the user can be formed, the user and the network must complete several other steps: initial connection of the user, selection of the primary O-RU and O-DU and formation of the measuring cluster. This section explains these steps and the different serving cluster formation methods. After these procedures, the physical layer processing for the UL signal is split between the cooperating O-RUs and O-DUs in the serving cluster. The O-RU applies the combining vector; the O-DU computes the combining vector, estimates the channel, and combines the signals from O-RUs using large-scale fading coefficients. The Near-RT RIC controls the O-DUs via the E2 interface [33]. This work considers a scenario with K users, D O-DUs, L O-RUs per O-DU, N antennas per O-

TABLE 2. List of the most commonly used symbols

Symbol	Definition	Symbol	Definition
K	Total number of users	D	Number of O-DUs
L	Number of O-RUs per O-DU	N	Number of antennas per O-RU
$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{l,k}$	Estimated channel vector between user k and O-RU l	$\mathbf{h}_{l,k}$	Channel Vector between user k and O-RU l
$\beta_{l,k}[t]$	Channel Gain between user k and O-RU l at time t	$\beta_{l,k}^{\text{dB}}[t]$	Channel gain between user k and O-RU l at time t expressed in dB
\mathcal{M}_k^s	Serving Cluster for user k at	\mathcal{M}_k^m	Measuring Cluster for user k
$O_k[t]$	Function that selects best O-RUs from measurement cluster for user k at time t	$Q_l^{(w)}[t]$	Function that selects w best users for O-RU l at time t
l_k^*	Index of primary O-RU for user k	K_l^*	Number of users that use O-RU l as primary O-RU
\mathbf{a}_k	LSFD combiner for user k	$\mathbf{v}_{l,k}$	Receive combiner for user k in O-RU l
$\mathcal{D}_l[t]$	Set of users that are served by O-RU l (served set) at time t	p_k	UL power of user k
$\mathbf{R}_{l,k}$	Covariance matrix of channel between user k and O-RU l	v_k	Speed of user k
$F_{l,k}[t]$	Shadow fading between user k and O-RU l at time t	τ_p	Length of the pilot sequence

RU, and a single Near-RT RIC. We assume all O-DUs and O-RUs are perfectly synchronised. We also denote the set of O-RUs connected to O-DU d as \mathcal{L}_d . We assume the UL and DL to be completely power-reciprocal.

A. Initial Connection, Primary O-RU and Measuring Cluster

When a user initially connects to the network, it first selects a **primary O-RU**, and the O-DU that controls that O-RU logically becomes the primary O-DU. The O-RU with the highest DL channel gain for the user is selected as the primary O-RU. The user computes that channel gain based on a downlink reference signal¹. The concept of the primary O-RU (and O-DU) is important in our network, as it determines:

- **Hard Handover:** The hard handover, as described in Section IV, occurs under specific conditions when a new primary O-RU is selected. Note that a new primary O-RU is selected based on decision rules discussed later, and it is not generally necessary to select a new primary O-RU each time a better O-RU is detected.
- **Measuring Cluster:** The measuring cluster is a set of O-RUs closest to the primary O-RU. With the primary O-RU, the measuring cluster is uniquely defined.
- **Signal Processing:** A user's primary O-DU computes the final estimate for that user's signal.

Based on the primary O-RU location, the Near-RT RIC forms a measuring cluster of O-RUs, \mathcal{M}_k^m , for that specific user k . The goal of the measuring cluster is to limit the number of O-RUs on which the channel gain should be measured when determining the serving clusters. The Near-RT RIC notifies every O-DU that controls an O-RU $l \in \mathcal{M}_k^m$ to track the UL channel gain, $\beta_{l,k}$, for that specific user k

¹We see this as a valid assumption as many works have argued in favour of DL pilots for DL signal processing, which is out of scope for this paper yet important for CF mMIMO systems [34].

in the relevant O-RUs streams via the E2 interface. These measurements serve to select an appropriate serving cluster. The size of the measuring cluster is thus one of the network parameters to be optimised. It brings an inherent trade-off between considering optimal O-RUs and signalling overhead to the RIC.

The initial access procedure, including the measuring cluster allocation, can then be summarised as follows:

- 1) A user completes an initial access procedure to the primary O-DU that controls the primary O-RU from which the user has the highest DL channel gain $\beta_{l,k}$.
- 2) The primary O-DU requests the Near-RT RIC to designate a measuring cluster for that user via the E2 interface.
- 3) The Near-RT RIC designates a set of O-RUs as a measuring cluster, \mathcal{M}_k^m , for a specific user. The O-DUs that control these O-RUs track the received power of the pilots of these users in the relevant O-RUs' streams.

B. Serving Cluster Formation

Finally, the serving cluster \mathcal{M}_k^s must be selected as a subset of the measuring cluster, \mathcal{M}_k^m , using one of the five cluster formation algorithms explained in the following subsections. This serving cluster performs joint precoding/decoding for a specific user k . Note that these O-RUs in the serving cluster can belong to one or multiple O-DUs, thus potentially requiring O-DUs to cooperate. We also define \mathcal{D}_l as the set of all users that are served by O-RU l .

Two **serving cluster** strategies are proposed in this section: a *Fixed* serving cluster formation and an *Opportunistic* serving cluster formation. The first one is fixed each time the user triggers a handover. With such handover, a new primary O-RU and measuring cluster are determined, and the Near-RT RIC statically defines a serving cluster based on the reported channel gain measurements. The opportunistic method allows each O-DU, doing the channel estimation for its O-RU in the measuring cluster for a particular user, to

locally decide if any of those O-RUs should aid the signal decoding for the considered user. We also consider three baseline methods: the method proposed by D'Andrea *et al.* [20], ubiquitous CF mMIMO and Cellular MIMO.

1) Fixed Cluster Formation

Under the fixed strategy, after the measuring cluster is obtained, the O-DUs that control the O-RUs in the measuring cluster report the UL channel gains, $\beta_{l,k}$, from user k to the Near-RT RIC over the E2 interface [5]. A fixed number of O-RUs with the highest UL channel gain become the serving cluster \mathcal{M}_k^s , and the user measures the metric \bar{P}_k , which is the sum of DL channel gains to user k when the cluster is created,

$$\bar{P}_k = \sum_{l \in \mathcal{M}_k^s} \beta_{l,k}. \quad (1)$$

This metric represents the total signal quality in the cluster when it is created. The sum DL channel gain is measured regularly and used to trigger handover, which will be discussed in Section IV. Let $O_k[t]$ be the function that maps the set of all O-RUs in the measuring cluster to a serving cluster which contains only the O-RUs with the highest UL channel gains from that user k at time t . The main advantage of this method is that the number of O-RUs is deterministic and chosen by the Near-RT RIC. The main disadvantage is significant signalling between the O-DUs and the Near-RT RIC each time a handover is triggered.

2) Opportunistic Cluster Formation

By the opportunistic method, after the allocation of the primary O-RU, primary O-DU and measuring cluster, the O-DUs decide locally if they serve a specific user on O-RUs that have unused processing capability and a good channel for that user without involving the Near-RT RIC. O-DUs decide opportunistically by only selecting O-RUs for the users with the highest respective UL channel gains. Since O-DUs decide autonomously, we need a way to limit the size of the serving cluster. We achieve this by having both a limited measuring cluster and placing an upper limit on the number of users a specific O-RU can serve opportunistically. In doing so, we attempt to only select the best users per O-RU. Thus, the O-DU selects the best users for each O-RU, and the size of the serving cluster is implicitly upper bound by the number of users per O-RU, which we denote by W and the size of the measuring cluster. Algorithm 1 shows how the O-RUs are loaded initially. In contrast to the fixed clustering strategy, this opportunistic strategy avoids a network-wide procedure executed at the Near-RT RIC.

The set of all users that are served by O-RU l , denoted by \mathcal{D}_l , has an upper limit W and firstly serves the K_l^* users that designated this O-RU l as primary O-RU. The O-RU l can then serve $w_l = W - K_l^*$ extra users. Let $Q_l^{(w_l)}[t]$ be the function that maps all the users whose measuring cluster

contains O-RU l as a non-primary O-RU to the subset of w_l users that achieve the best channel towards O-RU l at time instance t . Notice the effect of the measuring cluster size on the number of O-RUs that serve a specific user, as only O-RUs in its measuring cluster can potentially serve that user. The main advantages of this method are the low computational cost and reduced load on the E2 interface. The only required signalling is the notification of the initial measuring clusters from the Near-RT RIC to the O-DUs, and all opportunistic decisions can be fully decentralised. The main disadvantage of this method is that there are no guarantees on the number of serving O-RUs beyond the primary O-RU.

3) Baseline Clustering

The method proposed in [20] is the baseline for benchmarking our proposed solutions. Initial cluster formation is achieved by selecting the $|\mathcal{M}_k^s|$ best O-RUs for each user. Their work does not consider limiting the number of measurements and thus requires significant overhead.

4) Ubiquitous Cell-Free

To understand the best possible performance, we consider the case where every user is served by every O-RU in the network, and thus $|\mathcal{M}_k^s| = DL$. Hence, this serves as an upper bound on the performance of all other clustering solutions. It is expected that performance is diminished when only part of the network is used to serve a specific user. We evaluate the performance gap between our method and the optimal (unscalable) case by comparing our methods to the ubiquitous mode.

5) Cellular Association

A final benchmark is the cellular case, where every user is served only by O-RUs connected to a single O-DU. Hence, only L O-RUs cooperate to serve a single user. The cellular case is used as a lower bound on the performance. The disadvantages are two-fold: first, the number of O-RUs is inherently limited due to the size of the O-DU; second, the cluster has a very low probability of being optimal.

Algorithm 1 Initial Opportunistic Cluster Formation ($t = 0$)

```

1: for  $k = 1 \dots K$  do
2:   Assign primary O-RUs
3:    $l_k^* = \arg \max_l \beta_{l,k}[0]$ 
4: end for
5: for  $l = 1 \dots DL$  do
6:   Additionally load each O-RU up to  $W$  users
7:    $\mathcal{D}_l[0] \leftarrow Q_l^{(W-K_l^*)}[0]$ 
8: end for

```

III. System Model

This work considers UL detection. This section describes the channel model, the UL detection, the channel estimation, and the combiner calculation. We first start with the small-scale fading channel model; then, we explain our large-scale model for accurate cluster formation performance analysis at discrete time intervals. We then explain how the UL signal can be processed at multiple O-DUs and O-RUs, given a specific serving cluster for each user. Finally, we explain how the network performance is measured at these discrete time intervals. This will be the basis for benchmarking the performance in later sections.

A. Channel Model

The UL channel between user k and an O-RU l , $\mathbf{h}_{l,k} \in \mathbb{C}^N$, is assumed to be Rayleigh fading and generated as follows,

$$\mathbf{h}_{l,k} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{R}_{l,k}), \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{l,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ is the covariance matrix of the channel. These covariance matrices are defined by the AoA of the signal at the O-RU and the path loss. The covariances are assumed to be known at their respective O-RU l and its O-DU. This is a valid assumption since they can be estimated from a relatively limited amount of samples [35].

Many works in the current state-of-the-art use the Jakes autocorrelation model [36] to model the channel under user mobility. The Jakes model considers the following temporal evolution of the channel via an autoregressive function,

$$\mathbf{h}_{l,k}[t] = \rho \mathbf{h}_{l,k}[t-1] + \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \bar{\mathbf{h}}_{l,k}, \quad (3)$$

where ρ corresponds to the autocorrelation coefficient between different channels and $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{l,k} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{R}_{l,k})$ corresponds to the innovation component generated independently from the previous sample. The channel gain is then $\beta_{l,k}[t] = \|\mathbf{h}_{l,k}[t]\|_2^2$. The autocorrelation coefficient is computed via a zeroth order Bessel function of the first kind as,

$$\rho = J_0(\pi D_s T_s), \quad (4)$$

where $D_s = 2f_c \frac{v}{c}$ is the doppler spread of the user's signal and T_s is the sample time of the simulation. The autocorrelation function tends to zero even for relatively short time intervals and low user speeds. Hence, this model generates almost purely independent channels and channel gains, as shown in Section VI. As such, we propose a method to evolve the path loss of the channel, $\beta_{l,k}[t]$, temporally to study the long-term evolution of clusters more practically.

B. Temporal Large-Scale Channel Model

For the large-scale channel model, we consider a dense urban environment. Our model is thus based on the 3GPP Urban Microcell Model [37]. The path loss between user k and O-RU l is modelled as,

$$\beta_{l,k}^{\text{dB}}[t] = -34.53 - 38 \log_{10}(d_{l,k}[t]) + F_{l,k}[t], \quad (5)$$

where $d_{l,k}[t]$ is the distance between the user and the O-RU at time t and $F_{l,k}[t]$ is the random shadow fading at

that moment. Thus, the path loss consists of a deterministic distance-based component and a stochastic component.

We now bring mobility into the model. The users start moving from their initial position at a random angle $\theta_k[0] \sim \mathcal{U}[0, 2\pi]$. Their speed, v_k , is fixed for each simulation run. They move in a straight line until they reach the edge of the grid. If they were to leave the grid at the next interval, their trajectory would be reflected in the grid with a random angle. Their position is updated as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} x[t] &= x[t-1] + v_k T_s \cos(\theta_k[t]) \\ y[t] &= y[t-1] + v_k T_s \sin(\theta_k[t]) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

If the O-RU deployment is dense, users are generally close to several O-RUs. A minor user movement will then significantly change the Angle of Arrival (AoA) for the received signal at those nearby O-RUs. This changes the covariance matrix of those channels significantly (cf. (8)). However, the large-scale fading is correlated between nearby locations since shadow fading is correlated for those locations [32].

That correlation of the shadow fading between those two points can be modelled as $e^{-\alpha d}$ [38], where d is the distance between the two locations and α is the reciprocal of the so-called decorrelation distance. The decorrelation distance is environment-specific, and this work uses $\alpha^{-1} = 20\text{m}$, which is typical for a European city [38]. Hence, we model shadow fading itself as an autoregressive function. A user moves a distance of $v_k T_s$ between two subsequent samples. The evolution of the shadow fading $F_{l,k}[t]$ is then modelled as,

$$F_{l,k}[t] = \rho_k F_{l,k}[t-1] + \sqrt{1 - \rho_k^2} F_{l,k}^{\text{new}}. \quad (7)$$

At every time instance, $F_{l,k}^{\text{new}}$ is a newly drawn shadow fading from the distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{sf}}^2)$. The first realisation of the shadow fading $F_{l,k}[0]$ is also drawn from this distribution. The variance of the random shadow fading is an environment-specific parameter. We take $\sigma_{\text{sf}} = 10$ here, which is typical for an urban environment [37].

Shadow fading plays an important role in the proposed solution because the measuring cluster is constructed by taking the closest O-RUs to the primary one. Since shadow fading occurs, the O-RUs closer to the user might not be optimal as they could experience significant shadow fading. In this case, O-RUs that are further away might provide a higher channel gain. Generally, the probability of further O-RUs being better than closer ones increases with increasing shadow fading variance. Furthermore, because we consider a dense deployment of O-RUs, a relatively small user movement could induce a significant change in the AoA for a particular user-O-RU association if these are close. Hence, the channel covariance matrices should be calculated at every time instance. We use the one-ring scattering model [39] to calculate the channel covariance matrix,

$$[\mathbf{R}_{l,k}]_{m,n}[t] = \beta_{l,k}[t] \int e^{2\pi j d_H(n-m) \sin(\bar{\phi})} f(\bar{\phi}, t) d\bar{\phi}, \quad (8)$$

where $f(\bar{\phi}, t)$ is the time-dependent distribution of the possible AoA. This distribution can be either Gaussian, Laplacian,

or uniform around the true angle of arrival for the signal. This work considers a uniform distribution, which is typical for a rich scattering environment,

$$\bar{\phi} = \phi + \delta, \quad \delta \sim U[-\xi, \xi], \quad (9)$$

where ϕ is the true angle of arrival, and ξ models the richness of the scattering environment, i.e. the AoA's distribution. This model provides a realistic basis for evaluating mobility management and shadow fading effects for CF mMIMO. However, its applicability to other environments requires further study, as decorrelation distances and AoA characteristics may vary significantly.

C. Channel Estimation

For the O-DU to accurately decode the users' signal, it must first estimate the UL channels. To estimate the channel, each user k transmits a pilot sequence $\phi_{t_k} \in \mathbb{C}^{\tau_p}$, where t_k is the pilot index allocated to user k . O-RU l receives the superposition of all of the users' pilots as $\mathbf{Y}_l \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times \tau_p}$. The O-DU estimates the respective channels independently per O-RU. The O-DU decorrelates the received pilot for user k in O-RU l as $\mathbf{y}_{l,k}^{(p)} = \mathbf{Y}_l \frac{\phi_{t_k}^*}{\sqrt{\tau_p}}$. The O-DU then calculates the Minimum Mean Squared Error (MMSE) channel estimates between user k and O-RU l , $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{l,k}$, as [40]

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{l,k} = \sqrt{\tau_p p_k} \mathbf{R}_{l,k} \left(\sum_{i:t_i=t_k} \tau_p p_i \mathbf{R}_{l,i} + \sigma_{\text{ul}}^2 \mathbf{I}_N \right)^{-1} \mathbf{y}_k^{(p)}, \quad (10)$$

where the transmit power of user k is p_k . We denote the covariance of the channel estimation error as $\mathbf{C}_{l,k}$. If multiple users share the same pilot, this is called pilot contamination and leads to a significant degradation of channel estimation quality. However, we would like to point out that the effect can be significantly alleviated given a reasonable ratio between users and available pilots, a proper pilot allocation strategy [41], [42] and power control of the UL pilot [43].

D. Receive Combining

Large-Scale Fading Decoding (LSFD) [9] fits nicely into the O-RAN architecture as the physical layer processing is split between the O-RUs and O-DUs. We employ this decoding scheme by having the primary O-DU calculate the LSFD weights [9] based on the effective gains in all of the O-RUs of the serving clusters. UL detection has three stages. First, each O-RU l locally estimates the signal $\hat{s}_{l,k}$ of its served users, $k \in \mathcal{D}_l$, and sends these local estimates to its respective O-DU over its fronthaul interface. Second, this O-DU d computes more accurate estimates for the user's signal \hat{s}_k^d based on the LSFD weights of the user's signal. These estimates are then combined at the user's respective primary O-DU to obtain the final estimate for the user's signal, \hat{s}_k . This signal combination at the secondary and primary O-DUs is organised such that the LSFD solution is found at the primary O-DU [5]. This interface between

two cooperating O-DUs is a concept that was explored in [4], [5]. The received signal at each O-RU is,

$$\mathbf{y}_l = \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{h}_{l,k} s_k + \mathbf{n}_l. \quad (11)$$

The fronthaul specification in O-RAN [44] supports transfers of the receive combining vector from the O-DU to the O-RU over the fronthaul or signalling of CSI to the O-RU for calculating the combining vector at the O-RU and synchronisation between the O-RU and the O-DU via the synchronisation plane of the fronthaul interface. Here, we assume that the O-DU computes a Local Partial MMSE (LP-MMSE) [8] receive combiner $\mathbf{v}_{l,k}$ for each of its O-RU - user associations,

$$\mathbf{v}_{l,k} = p_k \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{D}_l} p_i \left(\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{l,i} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{l,i}^H + \mathbf{C}_{l,i} \right) + \sigma_{\text{ul}}^2 \mathbf{I}_N \right)^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{l,k}. \quad (12)$$

This is where the signal processing is linked to the serving clusters \mathcal{M}_k^s from Section II. The O-DU only computes this combiner for users served on its O-RUs. Since the combiner is computed per O-RU, the inverted matrix in (12) is only N by N , and thus leads to only a small processing delay. The O-RU then locally combines the received signal via $\mathbf{v}_{l,k}$ for all the users that it serves as

$$\hat{s}_{l,k} = \mathbf{v}_{l,k}^H \mathbf{y}_{l,k}, \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{M}_k^s. \quad (13)$$

To efficiently combine local estimates from O-RUs, we combine them based on statistics of the signal at each of these O-RUs, i.e., LSFD. To this end, we introduce the notation \mathbf{g}_{ki} which is the effective gain for user i in the receive combiner for user k and $\delta_{l,k}$ indicates if user k is served by O-RU l . These \mathbf{g}_{ki} are then defined as,

$$\mathbf{g}_{ki} = [\delta_{1,k} \mathbf{v}_{1,k}^H \mathbf{h}_{1,i} \quad \delta_{2,k} \mathbf{v}_{2,k}^H \mathbf{h}_{2,i} \quad \dots \quad \delta_{DL,k} \mathbf{v}_{DL,k}^H \mathbf{h}_{DL,i}]^T. \quad (14)$$

We denote the set of users that share at least one O-RU with user k as \mathcal{S}_k and assume that only those users induce significant interference towards user k . The primary O-DU calculates the LSFD weights $\mathbf{a}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{DL}$ for user k as [45],

$$\mathbf{a}_k = p_k \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_k} \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{g}_{ki} \mathbf{g}_{ki}^H\} + \mathbf{N}_k \right)^{-1} \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{g}_{kk}\}, \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{N}_k is defined as

$$\mathbf{N}_k = \sigma_{\text{ul}}^2 \text{diag} \left(\mathbb{E}\{\|\delta_{1,k} \mathbf{v}_{1,k}\|\}, \dots, \mathbb{E}\{\|\delta_{DL,k} \mathbf{v}_{DL,k}\|\} \right). \quad (16)$$

The vector \mathbf{a}_k has $|\mathcal{M}_k^s|$ non-zero elements. The LSFD weights are only a function of the channels' statistics; thus, the secondary O-DUs do not need to pass any channel estimates to the primary O-DU. We expect that the processing and communication delay for the primary O-DU combining does not significantly affect the performance due to the expected values of the effective channels being coherent for longer than the actual channels. Furthermore, they can be combined in the primary O-DU over longer intervals for

FIGURE 1. Overview of the O-DU/O-RU and the inter-O-DU signalling required for the cooperative detection. In the left (primary) O-DU, both O-RUs are used in decoding; on the right (secondary) O-DU, only the top O-RU is used. The O-DUs compute the combining vectors $\mathbf{v}_{l,k}$ for their respective O-RUs and transmit them via their fronthaul interface. The primary O-DU computes the LSFD combining vector \mathbf{a}_k and sends it to the other O-DUs involved in the decoding for user k . The O-RUs compute the local estimate for their users' signals $\hat{s}_{l,k}$ and send this to their O-DU. The O-DUs combine these signals to a local estimate \hat{s}_k^c and send this to the users' primary O-DU, where the final estimate is computed.

joint decoding without requiring much computational load and signalling between different O-DUs [40]. The statistics of different O-RUs are uncorrelated, and thus, the primary O-DU combines only the statistics of its own O-RUs and the O-RUs of secondary O-DUs without any error [5], i.e.

$$\mathbb{E}\{\{\mathbf{g}_{ki}\}_l\{\mathbf{g}_{ki}^*\}_r\} = \mathbb{E}\{\{\mathbf{g}_{ki}\}_l\}\mathbb{E}\{\{\mathbf{g}_{ki}^*\}_r\} \quad l \neq r. \quad (17)$$

The secondary O-DUs only need to give the primary O-DU timely updates of these channel statistics. We consider the relevant statistics to be known at the O-DU for each user served by its' O-RUs. At every timestep T_s , we check if a new cluster is needed, possibly update the cluster, and then always update the LSFD weights. Future work should also consider updates of the LSFD weights based on a metric for their ageing without necessarily updating the cluster. From the primary O-DU to the secondary O-DU, the only signalling required is the relevant elements of \mathbf{a}_k to the O-RUs of this secondary O-DU, which are in the serving cluster of user k . We assume these \mathbf{a}_k 's can be signalled to the relevant O-RUs with negligible delay over their respective fronthaul interfaces. We denote the set of O-RUs connected to O-DU d as \mathcal{L}_d . O-DU d locally combines the signals for each user served by O-RU $l \in \mathcal{L}_d$ and the primary O-DU combines the estimates of the serving O-DUs, \hat{s}_k^d ,

$$\hat{s}_k = \sum_{d=1}^D \hat{s}_k^d = \sum_{l \in \mathcal{M}_k^s} [\mathbf{a}_k^*]_l \hat{s}_{l,k}. \quad (18)$$

This result is transparent to how the O-RUs are organised amongst the different O-DUs. In our proposed architecture, computational load is divided amongst the O-DUs, which enables us to scale the algorithm across many O-RUs and O-DUs. Figure 1 highlights where each functional block is placed in the primary and secondary O-DUs and O-RUs.

E. Spectral Efficiency

The ergodic SINR is estimated as [45]:

$$\text{SINR}_k^{\text{ul}} = \frac{p_k |\mathbf{a}_k^H \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{g}_{kk}\}|^2}{\mathbf{a}_k^H \mathbf{D}_k \mathbf{a}_k}, \quad (19)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{D}_k = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_k} p_i \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{g}_{ki} \mathbf{g}_{ki}^H\} - p_k \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{g}_{kk}\} \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{g}_{kk}^H\} + \mathbf{N}_k. \quad (20)$$

The average spectral efficiency (SE) is then calculated from the SINR via: $\text{SE}_k^{\text{ul}} = \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_k^{\text{ul}})$. This performance metric is used in Section VI to show the performance of the clustering and handover strategies.

IV. Handover

Maintaining good user-centric clusters is crucial for maintaining performance under user mobility. However, if a serving cluster can only use a subset of the O-RUs in the network and users are mobile, any selected subset of O-RUs will become suboptimal as the user moves away from its cluster. Hence, in this section, we propose updating strategies for the initial clusters from Section II. For the fixed clustering, we define a performance threshold \bar{P}_k for the entire cluster based on the DL power received by the user. For the opportunistic cluster, we define a local threshold such that O-DUs with measuring O-RUs can locally decide which users to serve on its O-RUs, and users can select their primary O-RU. The Near-RT RIC is a perfectly suited central controller for handover management since it works in timescales between 10 ms and 1s. On the one hand, for the fixed clustering and handover, it must only select the O-RU with the highest channel gains. On the other hand, for opportunistic clustering and handover, the Near-RT RIC is mainly used to track which O-RU is each user's primary O-RU. As such, we believe that all proposed solutions can be implemented within the aforementioned timescales. We discuss these handover procedures at discrete times $t = nT_s$.

A. Handover for Fixed Clustering

For our fixed clustering strategy, the user continually compares the initial DL received power \bar{P}_k in the cluster to the current received DL power P_k . A hysteresis threshold M_{HO}^{F} is used to reduce the so-called 'ping-pong' effect. The user triggers a handover if the relative change of received power exceeds the hysteresis threshold, i.e.

$$\frac{\bar{P}_k - P_k}{\bar{P}_k} > M_{\text{HO}}^{\text{F}}. \quad (21)$$

By using a cluster-wide handover threshold, the total number of handovers can be reduced for large clusters since the total DL received power remains stable for relatively long periods.

The handover threshold brings a trade-off in the system's performance (higher SE) versus less signalling overhead (less frequent handovers). When the user triggers a handover, it selects a new primary O-RU with the highest DL channel gain. The new primary O-DU then requests a new measuring cluster around the new primary O-RU and, subsequently, a serving cluster for that user from the Near-RT RIC.

B. Opportunistic Cluster Tracking

In opportunistic tracking, the serving cluster updates on two levels: 1) The primary O-RU can change, which also implies a new measurement cluster; 2) The opportunistic reload where secondary O-RUs in the serving cluster depend on opportunistic decisions by measuring O-DUs. This creates a great opportunity for fine-grained mobility management. The control plane is kept persistent over long periods by selecting a higher threshold on the handover of the primary O-RU. Extra O-RUs can be added to the serving cluster to facilitate extra throughput without triggering an additional primary O-RU handover.

User-Triggered Primary O-RU Handover: The user triggers a primary O-RU handover when a new O-RU with a significantly higher DL channel gain is detected. As the primary O-RU is crucial for guaranteeing minimal service to the user, it is reasonable to make the user responsible for this tracking. Also, this reduces signalling in the network. We assume a hard handover is only needed if the new primary O-RU is outside the old serving cluster. This new best O-RU is then the new primary O-RU, and the Near-RT RIC allocates a new measurement cluster around that O-RU in the same manner as the initial measurement cluster, i.e., the closest O-RUs to the primary O-RU are selected. As primary O-RU allocation has priority in the network, this new O-RU drops a user if needed to satisfy the maximum number of users per O-RU constraint.

Algorithm 2 Opportunistic Cluster Tracking

```

1: At every time  $t$ 
2: for  $k = 1 \dots K$  do
3:    $\bar{l} \leftarrow \arg \max_l \beta_{l,k}^{\text{dB}}$ 
4:   if  $(\beta_{\bar{l},k}^{\text{dB}}[t] > \beta_{l^*,k}^{\text{dB}}[t] + M_{HO}^{O,P}) \wedge (\bar{l} \neq l^*)$  then
5:     Primary O-RU handover
6:      $\mathcal{D}_{l^*}[t] \leftarrow Q_{l^*}^{(W-Kl^*+1)}[t]$ 
7:      $l_k^* \leftarrow \bar{l}$ 
8:      $\mathcal{D}_{\bar{l}}[t] \leftarrow Q_{\bar{l}}^{(W-K\bar{l})}[t]$ 
9:   end if
10: end for
11: for  $l = 1 \dots L$  do
12:   if  $\exists k \notin \mathcal{D}_l[t] : \beta_{l,k}^{\text{dB}}[t] > \beta_{l,k}^{\text{dB}}[t] + M_{HO}^{O,S}, k \in \mathcal{D}_l[t]$  then
13:     Opportunistic O-RU Reload
14:      $\mathcal{D}_l[t] \leftarrow Q_l^{(W-Kl)}[t] \cup \{k : l_k^* = l\}$ 
15:   else
16:      $\mathcal{D}_l[t] \leftarrow \mathcal{D}_l[t-1]$ 
17:   end if
18: end for

```

Opportunistic O-RU Reload: Additionally, the O-DUs can dynamically change the set of users it opportunistically serves with its O-RUs. Once an O-DU detects a user with a significantly higher UL channel gain than the users it is currently serving on one of its O-RUs, the O-DU updates the served set for that O-RU opportunistically. The O-DU achieves this by selecting the users with that O-RU

in their measuring cluster with the highest UL channel gains (via $Q_l^{(u)}[t]$ from Section 2). Any changes in the opportunistic serving cluster can happen dynamically, as this does not change any connections between users and their primary O-RU. We use different thresholds for the primary handover and opportunistic O-RU reload. $M_{HO}^{O,P}$ and $M_{HO}^{O,S}$, respectively. We provide pseudocode in Algorithm 2.

C. Baseline Handover

Algorithm 3 Baseline [20]

```

1: For every time  $t$ 
2: for  $k = 1 \dots K$  do
3:    $m_k^- = \arg \min_{m \in \mathcal{M}_k^s[t-1]} \beta_{l,k}[t-1]$ 
4:    $m_k^+ = \arg \max_{m \notin \mathcal{M}_k^s[t-1]} \beta_{l,k}[t]$ 
5:   if  $\frac{\beta_{m_k^+,k}[t] - \beta_{m_k^-,k}[t-1]}{\beta_{m_k^-,k}[t-1]} > M_{HO}^B$  then
6:      $\mathcal{M}_k^s[t] \leftarrow \mathcal{M}_k^s[t-1] \setminus m_k^- \cap m_k^+$ 
7:   end if
8: end for

```

By the method in [20], handover is triggered whenever there is an O-RU outside of the serving cluster, which has a significantly higher channel gain than the worst O-RU in the serving cluster, thus requiring the Near-RT RIC to decide centrally on potential handover decisions. The authors of [20] also did not consider how to manage the control plane and keep this persistent during handover. Pseudocode is provided in Algorithm 3.

D. Ubiquitous Cell-Free

By this method, the user is served by every O-RU in the network. The user can move anywhere without significant losses because the LSFD combiner can calculate new combining weights \mathbf{a}_k based on the changing channel for every O-RU. Hence, there is no handover needed. However, it is helpful to highlight the performance gap to this method.

E. Cellular Handover

For the cellular baseline, a user requests a handover when it detects that it has significantly higher DL channel gains to an O-RU in a different O-DU than the one by which it is currently served. After empirical tuning, we set the handover threshold to $M_{HO}^C = 2$ dB.

V. Overhead

To improve the practicality of this work, we provide an overview of the associated costs. In the numerical results, we will show that, in general, enlarging the measuring or serving clusters improves performance with diminishing returns. Unfortunately, these enlargements come associated with specific costs that we can quantify to a large extent. In the following section, we analyse these costs.

The costs are split amongst many levels, most occurring at different frequencies. We sort them here from least to

TABLE 3. Costs associated with different procedures for the different clustering and association methods, all expressed per user.

	Method	Ubiquitous	Cellular	Fixed	Opportunistic
Clustering Overhead (every T_s)	Hard Handover	0	0	$p^{HO} \mathcal{M}_k^m $	$p^{HO} \mathcal{M}_k^m $
	Secondary O-RU selection	0	0	$p^{HO}(\mathcal{M}_k^m - 1)$	0
LSFD Decoding (every T_s)	LSFD Weight Calculation	$C_{LSFD}(DL)$	$C_{LSFD}(L)$	$C_{LSFD}(\mathcal{M}_k^s)$	$C_{LSFD}(\mathcal{M}_k^s)$
	Inter-DU Signal Samples	$(DL - D)\tau_u$	0	$(\mathcal{M}_k^s - 1)\tau_u$	$(\mathcal{M}_k^s - 1)\tau_u$
	Inter-DU Statistics	$DL - D$	0	$ \mathcal{M}_k^s - 1$	$ \mathcal{M}_k^s - 1$
Local Decoding (Every Coherence Block ($\tau_u + \tau_p$))	Channel Estimation	$DLC_{Channel}$	$LC_{Channel}$	$ \mathcal{M}_k^s C_{Channel}$	$ \mathcal{M}_k^s C_{Channel}$
	MMSE Combiners	DLC_{MMSE}	LC_{MMSE}	$ \mathcal{M}_k^s C_{MMSE}$	$ \mathcal{M}_k^s C_{MMSE}$
	User-Plane Fronthaul	$DL\tau_u$	$L\tau_u$	$ \mathcal{M}_k^s \tau_u$	$ \mathcal{M}_k^s \tau_u$

most frequent: 1) cluster formation, 2) LSFD combiner calculation and inter-O-DU signalling of channel statistics, 3) local channel estimation and MMSE combiner calculation, and 4) combiner application, user-plane inter-O-DU data transmission and LSFD combining weight application. Computational and signalling costs are expressed in floating-point multiplications and floating-point numbers to be transmitted, respectively. These costs are summarized in Table 3.

A. Clustering Overhead

Determining and redefining the initial clusters is associated with specific costs. On the one hand, for the fixed clustering, upon triggering handover for a user, $|\mathcal{M}_k^m|$ path loss values are transmitted to the Near-RT RIC over the E2 interface and compared for that user. A new cluster is formed, and $|\mathcal{M}_k^m|$ and $|\mathcal{M}_k^s|$ O-RUs are notified that they now belong to that user's measuring and serving cluster, respectively.

On the other hand, for opportunistic clustering, the O-DUs monitor those path loss values locally. Upon triggering a hard handover for a user, the Near-RT RIC is notified of the new primary O-RU for that user. The Near-RT RIC then notifies $|\mathcal{M}_k^m|$ O-RUs that they now belong to that user's measuring cluster.

We hereby introduce the variable p^{HO} , which indicates the probability of hard handover occurring every T_s . It can be obtained empirically from the figures presented in Section VI via the handover frequency. It should be noted that this probability depends on the chosen strategy, the chosen parameters, and the simulation setup.

For both methods, the computational cost of handover is conditioned on two main parameters: $|\mathcal{M}_k^m|$ and p^{HO} . The former can be chosen directly in the Near-RT RIC and the latter can be controlled by tuning their respective hysteresis thresholds. More importantly, it does not scale with the total network size for both methods. This highlights the practicality of the proposed measuring clusters; by limiting the number of O-RUs to which the user can be handed over, the algorithms become scalable.

The Near-RT RIC is not involved in the ubiquitous and cellular strategies. Because the user is connected to every O-RU or the user tracks the path loss to different nearby O-RUs for those strategies, respectively.

B. LSFD Decoding

The cost of computing an LSFD combiner is,

$$C_{LSFD}(|\mathcal{M}_k^s|) = |\mathcal{M}_k^s|^2 + \frac{|\mathcal{M}_k^s|^3 - |\mathcal{M}_k^s|}{3}. \quad (22)$$

It is important to note that this LSFD combiner remains constant for a period of T_s . Since the combiner is based on signal statistics, it must not be computed as often [40] which saves significant computing power and inter-O-DU signalling. These weights must, however, still be applied to every signal sample. For the signalling of inter-O-DU statistics, we assume a worst-case scenario where only one O-RU is used from the primary O-DU, and this O-DU thus needs statistics from $|\mathcal{M}_k^s| - 1$ O-RUs of other O-DUs. Similarly, we assume the same worst-case scenario for transmitting the signal samples between O-DUs.

C. Local Decoding

For the local decoding at the O-DUs, we consider the channel estimation, the combiner calculation and the combiner application. The cost of channel estimation per user-O-RU association at the O-DU is,

$$C_{Channel} = (N\tau_p + N^2). \quad (23)$$

The channel must be estimated once per coherence block. Computation of the LP-MMSE combiner at the O-DU costs,

$$C_{MMSE} = N^2 + \frac{N^3 - N}{3}. \quad (24)$$

This LP-MMSE combiner must be computed once per coherence block. Applying this combiner requires N complex multiplications per user-O-RU association.

VI. Simulation and Numerical Results

Our results are divided into three parts. Firstly, we validate our temporal channel model. Secondly, we analyse the static case for our proposed clustering approaches and then dimension our algorithms for the mobile case to increase the tractability of selected parameters. Thirdly, we provide numerical results for a mobile scenario. We pay particular attention to the trade-offs between handover frequency and performance and signalling overhead and performance.

The simulations are generated as follows. The users are placed randomly in a square grid according to a uniform distribution. This grid is divided into uniformly sized squares

for each O-DU, and the O-RUs for a specific O-DU are placed randomly in its O-DU's subsquare via a uniform distribution. We consider a configuration with 6×6 O-DUs. We duplicate the initial setup eight times to create a wrap-around scenario. The setup is then pruned to the 100 O-RUs nearest to the simulation's centre. User speeds range from pedestrian (3 km/h) to vehicular (50 km/h). The parameters for the simulation are summarised in Table 4.

TABLE 4. Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
K	25	Total O-RUs	100
D	36	N	4
L	4	Grid Size	0.5 x 0.5 km
Number of Setups	50	τ_p	25
T_s	0.1s	Simulation Time	60s
ξ	10°	σ_{ul}^2	-94 dBm
σ_{sf}	10	α^{-1}	20 m
p_k	100 mW		

A. Channel Model

To show that Jakes model is not fit for our analysis, i.e., long-term path loss evolution, we calculate the empirical Pearson autocorrelation ($\zeta(\beta_{l,k}[t], \beta_{l,k}[t + \Delta])$) coefficients of the path loss derived for both channel models. We use this coefficient since it will tell us how similar two instances of path loss are as a function of the time passed between those two instances. A high value indicates that the path losses are similar and vice versa. The empirical Pearson correlation coefficient between two variables x and y is expressed as,

$$\zeta(x, y) = \frac{n \sum_i x_i y_i - \sum_i x_i \sum_i y_i}{\sqrt{n \sum_i x_i^2 - (\sum_i x_i)^2} \sqrt{n \sum_i y_i^2 - (\sum_i y_i)^2}}. \quad (25)$$

The proposed model in (5) is based on empirical measurements of large-scale fading. The Jakes model is derived for minor movements via geometrical calculations. Many current works use this model to evolve the channel over time to study short-term channel ageing. Figure 2 shows the autocorrelation coefficients for different speeds as a function of the time difference between two samples. We observe that the Jakes model produces entirely random channel gains. This makes sense as the model is aimed at small-scale fading and is unfit for modelling long-term, large-scale fading evolutions. On the other hand, our model has a clear correlation between the different time samples due to correlated shadow fading, based on measurements [32].

B. Static Users

We first analyse the performance of the different clustering schemes for static users since this reduces the number of parameters (different handover thresholds and user speeds) and can serve as an upper bound on the performance for mobile users since user mobility will surely degrade the performance. Since different parameters influence our

two proposed strategies, we provide separate analyses. We benchmark both methods on the number of O-RUs allocated to each user and the median SE. As the cluster size increases, SE improves due to the increased diversity and beamforming gains. However, the performance improvement saturates [5] while costs (cf. Table 3) keep rising.

1) Fixed Clustering

By the fixed clustering strategy, the cluster size is deterministic and can be controlled by the Near-RT RIC. Furthermore, the Near RT RIC always selects the O-RUs with the highest channel gains for the users. The sizes of the measuring cluster and the serving cluster control the performance entirely in the static case. The size of the measuring cluster brings an essential trade-off between signalling overhead (for cluster computation) and performance (selecting optimal O-RUs for every user). To this end, we empirically measure the probability of each O-RU inside the measuring cluster having a higher channel gain than the best O-RU outside of the measuring cluster. We denote this probability by P_{opt} .

Figure 3 shows this result for serving cluster sizes of 4, 8, and 16 O-RUs. For a small serving cluster size (4 O-RUs), the optimal cluster can likely be found with a relatively small measuring cluster. However, when the serving cluster is large, a considerably large measuring cluster is needed to find the best O-RUs. This becomes rather expensive for the fixed clustering strategy, as the Near-RT RIC must track all $|\mathcal{M}_k^m|K$ O-RU - user channel gains.

Figure 4 therefore shows the median SE as a function of the size of the measuring cluster for the fixed clustering strategy. If the serving cluster is small, the measuring cluster can also be chosen relatively small. Increasing the measurement set beyond the serving set size gives extra degrees of freedom to select O-RUs but does not significantly impact performance beyond a certain saturation point. For example, for a serving cluster size of 6, SE is improved by 41% if the measurement cluster is increased from 6 to 100. However, a measurement cluster size of 16 already gives 36% of that gain. This leads us to believe that finding the absolutely best O-RUs for a large serving cluster is unnecessary, as many of these O-RUs will be quite far from the user anyway. Due to the large user-O-RU distances, these O-RUs only provide marginal gains to SE, even though they have a relatively higher channel gain than other O-RUs. We conclude that a small measurement cluster is sufficient to achieve most of the potential performance and can increase scalability by reducing the signalling to the Near RT RIC.

2) Opportunistic Clustering

For opportunistic clustering, the problem becomes more complex, as even for a static scenario, there is already an interplay between two defining parameters: the measuring cluster size, and the number of users per O-RU W . Since

(a) Channel gains from Jakes autocorrelation model (3)

(b) Proposed Model in (5)

FIGURE 2. Empirical Pearson Autocorrelation Coefficients of the channel gain as a function of time difference $\zeta(\beta_{t,k}[t], \beta_{t,k}[t + \Delta])$ for users moving at different speeds.

FIGURE 3. Fixed Clustering: Empirical P_{opt} in function of the size of the measuring cluster $|\mathcal{M}_k^m|$ for different sizes of the serving cluster, $|\mathcal{M}_k^s|$ for static users.

FIGURE 4. Fixed Clustering: Median SE as a function of the size of the measuring cluster for different serving cluster sizes over 100 shadowing realisations for static users.

the O-DU can locally decide to serve users, the size of the serving cluster for each user becomes random and is strongly affected by the size of the measuring cluster. However, due to the contention mechanism on the O-RU, the parameter W also has a significant impact. To this end, we have studied the impact of the maximum number of users served by a single O-RU, W .

First, Figure 5a demonstrates the effect of the measuring cluster. The number of O-RUs allocated to each user is shown for a fixed maximum number of users to be served by a single O-RU ($W = 6$). Enlarging the measuring

cluster leads to more variations in the number of O-RUs that effectively serve each user. This is due to the more pronounced effect of the contention mechanism at the O-RUs. When the measuring cluster is small, there is little overlap in clusters for each user. Thus, the user will likely be connected to most O-RUs in the measuring cluster. As the measuring cluster grows, so does the contention among users, thus impacting the serving cluster’s size and increasing the variations thereof. We suspect that this effect is not as pronounced for $|\mathcal{M}_k^m| = 100$ due to the limited size of our simulation area.

Second, Figure 5b explores the effect of the contention mechanism for the O-RU resources by taking a large measurement cluster $|\mathcal{M}_k^m| = 100$ and varying W . The result indicates that if the measuring cluster is large, the distribution of the cluster sizes is very tight. Furthermore, even for a large amount of contention, i.e., a small number of users on every O-RU and very large measuring clusters, the distribution is tight around its’ mean. Overall, if the measuring cluster is large and the maximum number of users per O-RU is small, the users receive a relatively fair number of O-RUs in their serving set. We assume a uniform user density. If the user distributions were non-uniform, the Near-RT RIC would allocate more O-RUs for users to specific user ‘hotspots’.

The question then arises about how this relative fairness regarding the number of O-RUs per user translates to actual performance. After all, the previous figures only indicate fairness regarding the number of serving O-RUs, not necessarily regarding actual performance. To this end, we have characterized the CDF of the SE of these two scenarios in Figure 6. Figure 6a shows mixed results. Even though the number of O-RUs per user is somewhat similar for smaller measuring clusters and served sizes W , the achieved SE is more broadly distributed. We assume that due to the reduced size of serving clusters, the network is not as good at alleviating the adverse effects of shadow fading. SE is not fairly distributed for the much larger serving sets, either. We suspect this is due to the contention mechanism at the O-RUs, which admits only the best users. Figure 6b shows

(a) Varying sizes of the measuring cluster $|\mathcal{M}_k^m|$ for fixed maximum number of users per O-RU $W = 6$

(b) Varying maximum number of users W for a fixed measuring cluster size of $|\mathcal{M}_k^m| = 100$

FIGURE 5. Opportunistic Clustering: CDF of the number of O-RUs serving each user $|\mathcal{M}_k^s|$. The results are gathered from 100 realisations of the shadow fading for static users.

(a) Varying sizes of the measuring cluster $|\mathcal{M}_k^s|$ for fixed maximum number of users per O-RU $W = 6$

(b) Varying maximum number of users per O-RU W for a fixed measuring cluster size $|\mathcal{M}_k^m| = 100$

FIGURE 6. Opportunistic Clustering: CDF of the SE for each user in the static case. The results are gathered from 100 realisations of the shadow fading for static users.

FIGURE 7. Opportunistic Clustering: Median SE as a function of the measuring cluster's size $|\mathcal{M}_k^m|$ for static users and different W . The results are gathered from 100 realisations of the shadow fading.

the SE's distribution for different sizes of served sets when the channels are measured on all user-O-RU associations.

Finally, Figure 7 demonstrates these effects via the median SE. Indeed, the scaling characteristic is similar to that of the fixed clustering strategy. The main difference, however, is the slow saturation when increasing the size of the served set. In stark contrast to the number of O-RUs in the serving

cluster, the mean SE does not increase much with W beyond six. Increasing this parameter beyond $W = 6$, a relatively low value, does not increase the system's performance much. For example, increasing W from 6 to 20 only increases median SE with 4% and 5% when measuring on 20 and 100 O-RUs, respectively. Furthermore, for $W = 6$, increasing the measurement cluster size from 42 to 100 only increases median SE with 9%. This result supports our findings from Figure 4, where median SE also does not increase much beyond this point for a comparable number of serving O-RUs. However, we must note that measurements are not expensive for the opportunistic strategy as they must only be compared locally. As such, we parametrize the mobile case to use a large measuring cluster of $|\mathcal{M}_k^m| = 30$ and $W = 4$.

C. Mobile Users

Finally, based on our analysis of the static scenario, we analyse the scenario where users are mobile. The performance of the clustering strategies is assessed by measuring the UL SE at discrete time intervals nT_s , $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and the handover frequency. We do not consider intra-frame channel ageing since we attempt to study the ageing of the clusters by itself

FIGURE 8. Fixed Clustering: Effect of the handover threshold M_{HO}^F for a fixed serving size of $|\mathcal{M}_k^s| = 10$ and a measurement size of $|\mathcal{M}_k^m| = 20$ for mobile users.

FIGURE 9. Opportunistic Clustering: Measuring cluster with a size of $|\mathcal{M}_k^m| = 30$, a secondary threshold, $M_{HO}^{O,S}$ of 4 dB and a $W = 4$ for different primary O-RU handover thresholds $M_{HO}^{O,P}$ for mobile users.

FIGURE 10. Fixed Clustering: Varying $|\mathcal{M}_k^s|$ for fixed handover thresholds $M_{HO}^F = 0.5$ and a fixed $|\mathcal{M}_k^m|$ of 40 for mobile users.

FIGURE 11. Opportunistic Clustering: Varying served sizes W for a fixed primary O-RU handover thresholds $M_{HO}^{O,P}$ of 7 dB, a secondary threshold, $M_{HO}^{O,S}$ of 4 dB and fixed measurement size $|\mathcal{M}_k^m|$ of 30 for mobile users.

instead of the ageing of the precoder or combiner as is done in [27], [28], [31].

First, the impact of the handover threshold is explored for both strategies. The fixed strategy only requires tuning a single handover threshold, which considers the relative reduction of received power at the user. The opportunistic strategy, however, considers two distinct handover thresholds, one for the primary and one for the secondary O-RUs. The primary threshold can thus be chosen much larger as extra O-RUs can opportunistically improve the rate of each user, and only the primary O-RU is vital for the persistence of the control plane. Regarding the baseline, we use the method from [20] with a threshold of $M_{HO}^B = 0.2$ and 4 serving O-RUs. The baseline is dimensioned with such a small serving cluster because the CPU has to track the path loss to every single AP in that serving cluster and then determine handover for those associations, thus resulting in significant overhead.

1) Thresholds

Fixed Strategy: Figure 8a and Figure 8b show the CDF of the SE for different handover thresholds for a user at 50 km/h and handover rates at different speeds, respectively, for the fixed strategy. Based on the results of Figure 4, we dimension the serving cluster with a size of 10 and a measuring cluster of 20. This gives most of the performance at a fraction of the computational cost. We find that, for the tested cluster size, the fixed clustering strategy is not very sensitive to the exact threshold, i.e., for users travelling at 50 km/h, we find that when decreasing the handover threshold from 0.75 to 0.1, median SE only increases by 11%. However, handover frequency increases from 0.15 to 0.69 handovers per second. Thus, a larger handover threshold significantly reduces the handover rate, yet the median SE at high speed (50 km/h) remains almost the same. This highlights one of the shortcomings of the fixed strategy: even though the number of O-RUs is determined at the RIC, the user tracks the received power. A significant reduction in the received power for a specific user will trigger a handover, but the achieved rate is only logarithmically related to this received power. Because we consider a relatively high SINR regime, the effect on SE becomes minor.

Opportunistic Strategy: For analyzing the opportunistic scheme, Figure 9a and Figure 9b show the CDF of the SE for different handover thresholds for a user at 50 km/h and hard handover rates at different speeds, respectively. The primary handover threshold also does not significantly affect the achieved SE. We argue that this is probably because the primary O-RU is only a minor part of the cluster serving each user (we find 10.75 O-RUs on average). This is a positive result as it allows us to maintain a low hard handover rate and a very high SE. After all, we expect the control plane not to require such a significant rate so we can keep it consistent (at the same O-RU) for a long time, i.e., the handover rate

for the opportunistic strategy with a primary threshold of 10 dB is only 0.23/s at a speed of 70 km/h. At the same time, median SE remains at 4.31 Bps/Hz, whereas the fixed scheme at a threshold of 0.5 only achieves 4.03 Bps/Hz while having a handover frequency of 0.29/s.

2) Cluster Size

Another important factor is the size of the serving cluster. Increasing the cluster size is also extremely useful to deal with user mobility. We find makes the system much more resilient against mobility and significantly reduces the number of handovers. This is a somewhat intuitive conclusion, as a large serving cluster allows the change of respective LSFD weights instead of requiring handover.

Fixed Strategy: Figure 10a and Figure 10b show the serving cluster size's effect on SE distribution and the average handover rate. Since the serving cluster grows large in this simulation and we want to study its effect exclusively, we use 40 O-RU in the measuring cluster. We conclude that the serving cluster size is much more important for performance tuning than the actual thresholds. Furthermore, increasing the size of the serving cluster has a significant impact on the handover rate. This should inspire network architects to dimension these serving clusters as rather large.

Opportunistic Strategy: Figure 11 explores the effect of W for the opportunistic clustering strategy for a scenario with mobile users. Increasing W significantly affects the SE and the handover rate. We suspect that the implicit effect on the size of the serving cluster mainly induces this change in the handover rate. Due to its increased size, the user rarely selects a new primary O-RU outside the cluster.

The results of the fixed and opportunistic strategies have led us to similar conclusions. We have found that a larger serving cluster is quite helpful in reducing the handover rate. This leads to an increased SE and reduced handover rate. We have found that tuning the serving cluster size is much more practical than tuning the handover parameters.

Furthermore, these results underline the benefits of having many O-DUs cooperate. Compared to the cellular case, performance is improved significantly. Consider especially the opportunistic strategy. The handover frequency is quite similar to the cellular case for a relatively small W and high handover threshold, but the achieved SE is much higher.

D. Pilot Contamination

Finally, the following section explores the effect of pilot contamination. The number of available pilots τ_p is now smaller than the total number of users K . The pilots are allocated randomly to the different users but in such a way that they are not reused more than necessary. We found that reusing pilots $\tau_p < K$ negatively affects the uplink performance, but the effect does not deteriorate the system's performance beyond a reasonable degree.

FIGURE 12. Fixed Strategy: Mean SE with a handover threshold of $M_{HO}^F = 0.5$ and 10 O-RUs serving each user with varying levels of pilot contamination.

FIGURE 13. Opportunistic Strategy: Mean SE with a measurement cluster size of 30 O-RUs, maximally four users per O-RU, a primary and secondary threshold of 7 dB and 4 dB, respectively, with varying levels of pilot contamination.

On the one hand, Figure 12 reveals that the fixed strategy is rather sensitive to pilot contamination. This is most likely caused by the larger number of O-RUs serving each user; thus, many users overlap on O-RUs. This leads to a deterioration of the mean UL SE by 6% at 3 km/h and a decrease of 4% at 70 km/h.

On the other hand, Figure 13 shows that the opportunistic strategy is rather robust to pilot contamination. This can be attributed to the number of users per O-RU being inherently limited (via W). Thus, even for a random assignment of pilots, the probability of having multiple users with the same pilot being served by the same O-RU is reduced compared to the fixed strategy, where no such mechanism exists. This is evident from the result since the mean UL SE only decreases by 3.6% at 3 km/h and only by 1.4% at 70 km/h.

Furthermore, the effect of pilot contamination is relatively less pronounced for fast-moving users since, in that case, there is a mixed effect of the pilot contamination and the reduced performance of the clusters (due to moving away fast from the allocated cluster). In short, we found that, for our tested scenario, it is not worth allocating the pilots centrally for the opportunistic strategy since the UL SE does not deteriorate significantly, and the centralized pilot allocation would incur major overhead.

VII. Conclusion

This work presents a comprehensive framework for mobility management in CF mMIMO at sub-6 GHz frequencies. A temporal channel model for correlated Rayleigh Fading based on empirical measurements is proposed. In contrast to most state-of-the-art, which mainly considers short-term channel ageing and uses the Jakes model, the proposed model is suited for studying long-term mobility management. Additionally, a framework that includes primary O-RUs, primary O-DUs, and serving and measuring clusters as an extension to the existing O-RAN architecture is presented. This framework allows cluster formation and mobility management in CF mMIMO networks with limited channel knowledge between users and O-RUs and O-DUs.

Two clustering and handover strategies are presented: an opportunistic strategy and a fixed strategy. These methods are then benchmarked in great detail. The results show that a large serving cluster can reduce handover overhead at the cost of an increased signal processing overhead. The opportunistic strategy proves particularly effective, achieving significant reductions in handover frequency and signalling overhead compared to centralized methods while maintaining high spectral efficiency. We conclude that efficient and reliable mobility management is possible even by taking local decisions at the O-DUs and that the negative effects of user mobility can be largely alleviated thanks to the inherent macro-diversity of CF mMIMO.

In conclusion, this work offers a significant step toward scalable mobility management in CF mMIMO networks. We proposed efficient, practical and flexible methods for cluster management. Our framework draws a clear path toward scalable and cost-effective 6G deployments leveraging local decision-making and integrating seamlessly with O-RAN.

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